

The Role of Neuropsychological Responses to Multisensory Dining Experiences

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Bachelor's Thesis
Glion Institute of Higher Education
2025

Acknowledgments

The completion of this thesis would not have been possible without the involvement, expertise, and inspiration provided by a number of individuals, both academic and personal, as well as one particularly determined Broadway legend.

Gratitude is owed to my thesis tutor, Pascal Christian, whose guidance brought clarity to complexity, whose criticism sharpened ideas, and whose steady support ensured the project remained not just on track, but intellectually engaging.

Recognition must be given to Dr. Ally Louks, whose prior research served as the intellectual spark behind this study. Her exploration of the subject matter offered not only a solid foundation but also the motivation to contribute something original to an evolving conversation.

This research, however, was not built on academics alone. Behind every deadline met stood a quiet pillar of unconditional support, my family whose belief in the pursuit of education never weakened. The encouragement extended during moments of hesitation, as well as the calm provided during moments of stress, were as essential as any library resource or data point.

As for the enduring presence of friendship, its value cannot be overstated. Those who offered unwavering companionship, shared laughter, and the occasional reminder to take a break were, in their own way, part of the research methodology.

To all survey participants who contributed their time and insight—this research owes much to their openness and engagement. The responses formed the backbone of the findings and brought theoretical frameworks to life.

Lastly, an unconventional but sincere nod must be made to a certain musical composition that played on loop during late-night writing sessions. The song “*Non-Stop*” from *Hamilton* by Lin-Manuel Miranda provided not just background noise but a rhythm of perseverance. Its relentless energy became a quiet collaborator in the final stretch of this work and the assurance – if Alexander Hamilton could write 51 essays with no access to the Internet in the 18th century – I can too.

Summary Page

Title: The Role Of Neuropsychological Responses To Multisensory Dining Experiences

Abstract

This study was conducted to explore the role of neuropsychological responses to multisensory dining experiences and their impact on perceived value and sustainable consumption behaviours. The research aimed to identify behavioural patterns associated with unconventional sensory environments, assess whether guest satisfaction in such contexts compromises ethical and environmental standards, and evaluate concept development strategies that balance creativity with sustainability.

A quantitative method was employed using a structured online survey distributed among individuals with interest or experience in multisensory dining. Sixteen Likert-scale questions, aligned with three research objectives, were used to capture data on sensory perceptions, value judgments, and sustainability intentions. Responses from 66 participants were collected and analysed using descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing based on the absolute majority principle.

Findings indicated a significant positive relationship between immersive sensory stimuli and enhanced perceived value, supporting previous literature on emotional engagement and dining satisfaction. However, results also revealed a tendency for emotional and aesthetic immersion to diminish critical awareness of sustainability,

often leading to passive trust and potential overconsumption. Despite this, the majority of participants expressed willingness to support ethical transparency and valued sustainable design when presented in a compelling, emotionally resonant manner.

It was concluded that multisensory dining environments hold the potential to influence both guest satisfaction and ethical behaviour, provided that sustainability is integrated seamlessly within the sensory experience. Recommendations were made for practitioners to embed transparency and responsibility into the storytelling and aesthetic design of experiential dining concepts.

Key Words: Olfactory, behaviour pattern, multisensory stimuli, 5 senses, immersive experience, environmental responsibility, perceived value.

Semester: 2025.02

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

In the last few years, the meaning of food and beverages has evolved drastically beyond the basic nourishment need into a fully immersive and emotionally driven experience, redefining the concept of modern luxury – where humanity, climbing higher on the Maslow’s pyramid, strives for more unique and niche impressions. That said, the rise of multisensory dining concept, where a meal stimulates all five human senses – sight, smell, touch, sound, and taste – has transformed the hospitality framework (Liu et al., 2023). The shift in the service quality proportionally affects customers’ expectations, making them more memorable and significant (Youssef & Spence, 2023), leading to restaurants and dining outlets starting to invest in design and creativity as well as incorporate new storytelling technologies into their daily operations due to the confirmed growing expectations of the guest providers (Velasco et al., 2024).

Multisensory dining, the newly introduced concept, enhances the guest satisfaction through creating a strong emotional connection, which is the main goal of any establishment associated with people, as discussed by Kleinhans et al. (2021). The best proven way to achieve that is by positively influencing all the human senses, rather than the primary one, as it promotes a more effective marketing impact due to the progressively shortening attention span (Chen et al., 2020). That said, what is

becoming more evident in modern dining concepts that follow the multisensory tactic is the careful curation of lighting, room scent, textures overall ambience – the stimuli which not only optimises the dining moment, but forges long-term loyalty and brand identity.

What once used to be considered as a functional act of consuming food is now seen as a theatrical event (Tsaur & Lo, 2020). This shift has reshaped the restaurant experience, especially in fine dining, where shareability and uniqueness are the quintessential factors. The appearance of what is on the plate, in combination with its surroundings such as the storytelling techniques and the design itself, contribute to the aesthetic value and consequently its social media relevance (Tsaur & Lo, 2020; Rottigni & Spence, 2024).

At the center of this growing trend lies neuropsychology – the study of how external stimuli influence perception and behaviour – in the given case -- studies this phenomenon for use in the hotel industry and examines the influence of external factors on the brain (Gao & Krashes, 2024). It was shown that seemingly minor factors that differ the place's ambience significantly alter guests' perception of overall experience on the unconscious level (Malcman et al., 2024). For example, a calmer and more sensory-aware music and lighting allow people to focus more on the food and the interlocutor, promoting mindful eating. On the other hand, overstimulation and

poor sensory alignment, namely loud and heavy music can result in distraction from the meal, discomfort and unconscious negative associations (Spence, 2020).

However, it is worth emphasizing that the neuropsychology-driven dining also poses certain risks and ethical considerations. Sensory cues might be used not only to intensify pleasure but also to manipulate guests into overconsumption, as it plays a role of an addictive element – the supply increases demand (Weijers et al., 2024). The result of such practices is both: negative opinion of the establishment, as sooner or later the manipulation is being disclosed by human brain, and, on a more global level, sustainability and environmental issues, such as unhealthy habits or overwaste (Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu, 2020).

Another crucial risk that can be evaluated is the personal hypersensitivity of certain individuals to some stimuli tools – odors/colors/sounds. Considering different cases of human responses – the multisensory dining establishments are exposed to the risk of not being fully inclusive – as individuals with both, specific intolerances or broadly known diagnoses (color blindness, autistic spectrum disorders, epilepsy, etc.) might not be always well-accommodated (Yuan et al., 2022).

As restaurants experiment with the neuropsychological approach, it remains necessary to weigh the psychological benefits and ethical considerations. On the one hand, it will help the establishment gain popularity and win the hearts of visitors. This will lead to increased profits and an improved reputation for the restaurant (Liu et al.,

2023). On the other hand, when influencing consumer behavior, the dining experience should be tailored to respect personal boundaries, health and sustainability, to avoid an unfavorable outcome (Gao & Krashes, 2024). As humankind evolves fast and the progress made in personal needs and perceptions of value cannot be reversed counterclockwise, the right balance between moving forward and building the future yet not damaging what was established in the past is essential.

This study explores how neuropsychological responses affect value perception in regard to the F&B industry. It studies the link between sensory input, behaviour, feelings, emotions and values of people, while at the same time assessing whether the pursuit of guest satisfaction may come at a cost of ethical and ecological malpractice (Youssef & Spence, 2023; Chen et al., 2020). Moreover, it discusses and tests the hypothesis of whether there is a way to balance out memorable and responsible dining experiences and investigate what is currently being done to achieve that goal (Tsaur & Lo, 2020).

1.2. Rationale For the Study

Over the past five years, the hospitality and F&B industries have evolved towards both health and emotionally conscious experiences. Increasingly more consumers have started prioritizing their health based on the 5 senses of sight, sound, smell, touch and taste (Kim et al., 2023). In response to that, restaurants commenced to invest more in recently discovered technologies and experiment with unconventional service strategies to meet the multidimensional expectations of the customers (Huang et al., 2023).

However, regardless of the growing number of literature on multisensory experiences, there is a gap in understanding the neuropsychological component of the new concept, specifically in the discussion of the perceived value and ethical dining outcomes. While there are articles that have already investigated the sensory stimulation in dining and which discuss the positive effect that new experiences have on perception development (Youssef & Spence, 2023; Spence, 2020; Rottigni & Spence, 2024), notably less authors have examined the negative influence of the stimuli, like the appearance of negative behaviour factors – overconsumption and unconscious decision-making (Gao & Krashes, 2024; Malcman et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the issue of balancing guest satisfaction and sustainability has not been thoroughly researched – despite Tsaur & Lo (2020), Yuan et al. (2022) having mentioned that the emotional satisfaction prevails over ethical considerations, there is a significant gap in material that effectively criticizes the lack of sustainable frameworks in concept development (Mejia & Wilson, 2024; Jose et al., 2025).

There are few researches that acknowledge the fact of existing developing strategies to promote creative yet sustainable experiences, such as the shift towards plant-based menu (Weijers et al., 2024), integrating green innovation (Ngo, 2024; Wei & Pujari, 2024), and introducing local touch (Baby et al., 2024) — but these are not normally focusing on the actual immersive dining – more of traditional fine-dining establishments. The purpose of this thesis is to bridge the gap between the two aforementioned pillars. The first step to achieve that goals is to explore how sensory manipulation may drive unintended consequences like overindulgence or cognitive overload (Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu, 2020).

Moreover, the existing literature emphasizes factors like scent, light, or music (Chen et al., 2020; Kleinhans et al., 2021), however only few studies have presented them as a neuropsychological framework within the topic of dining experiences. This thesis is aimed on fulfilling the need to link consumer behavior to ethical misconduct,

which would contribute for a more conscious and relative approach for the concept development and experience creation practices.

1.3. Aim and objectives

The aim of this study is to examine whether multisensory dining and unconventional F&B concepts increase perceived value or whether they promote unsustainable overconsumption behaviours, in order to investigate potential opportunities for creating immersive yet sustainable dining experiences.

To achieve this aim, three objectives were created:

Objective 1:

To identify and observe patterns of neuropsychological effects of unconventional dining on perceived value and consumption behaviour.

Objective 2:

To assess if modern dining concepts provide guest satisfaction at the cost of unethical and unsustainable practices.

Objective 3:

To evaluate existing concept development strategies for balancing creativity in dining and environmental responsibility.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Sensory Experiences

One of the most discussed topic in fine dining industry and in hospitality in general is how sensory factors stimulate neuropsychological responses and affect guest behaviour in hospitality settings. As Youssef and Spence (2023) explored in their research, “gastromotive dining” was designed to show the connection between emotional and sensory level, leading to a deeper sense of immersion and value perception. What is more, they mention that elements that restaurants are using on a daily basis like smell, sounds, light and textures create an emotional resonance that raises overall satisfaction while guest is having a meal.

Spence (2020) further explored the influence of ambient odors in a fine dining restaurant and stated that they can evoke emotions and memories, thus unconsciously alter the perception of the flavor. Velasco et al. (2024) highlighted that technology also plays a major role in deepening emotional engagement. They based this hypothesis on an example of a wine tasting during which the digital tools were used. Authors stated that usage of digital tools can significantly impact the overall experience as participants start to feel more emotionally involved. In addition, Velasco et al. (2024) also mentioned a different vector of thought – the combination between digital tools complement multisensory experiences in a way that with this combination the

emotional immersion strengthens and providing for a higher customer satisfaction index.

The other pillar that plays an important factor in mental connection with the establishment is environmental design. Following the idea that Yuan et al. (2022) mentioned in their research -- the well-designed dining spaces that perform a combination of formality, thought-through layout and customer involvement influence the scale of how deeply the place is remembered afterwards. The similar thought can be seen in the research by Kleinhans et al. (2021), who stated that décor, aroma and acoustic ambience indeed summon different neuropsychological responses and could potentially trigger the how consumers feel and behave in public dining spaces.

Rottigni and Spence (2024) provided as an example the extraordinary experiment where it was documented that people reportedly cried during an immersive sensory dessert experience. Their research explains that the combination of engagement combined with storytelling during the meal can evoke one of the most powerful emotions, which is an excellent example of neuropsychological and emotional responses activate during dining experience. In the same way, Malcman et al. (2024), has conducted a similar experiment, in the process of which it was shown that the music tempo can also affect the consumer's behavior. They found out that music that guests hear in the background in the restaurants can influence not only the meal

duration, but also the tipping behaviour, showing that physical and mental responses of the human body can be translated into measurable consumption outcomes.

Gao and Krashes (2024) gave another significant example. They highlighted in their research that brain is the regulator of food intake process that can be affected by different things like noises, lights, which sometimes lead to those mental and emotional responses override the internal satiety signal. According to their study, the restaurant that is offering bigger meal portions tend to be more attentive to the external factors that are mentioned above. Their finding confirms that portion control and well-designed layout and establishment's environment are tightly linked through neural cases.

Another study conducted by Chen et al. (2020) also explains that there is a chance to affect the multisensory perspective with non-food-elements. For instance, by adding floral arrangements and olfactory stimulation, similar to what can be observed during the aromatherapy in SPA. That said, the atmosphere of a dining places that use strategic and global sensory integration has a huge potential to activate the brain's reward centres and increase loyalty and perceived value (Chen et al., 2020). Tsaur and Lo (2020) mentioned the same in their research by developing a model to measure the impact of sensory and emotional stimuli in fine dining context. This leads to the point that having an unexpected and unique experience can influence both memory and intention to revisit the place.

These research findings clearly state that neuropsychological responses to multisensory dining experiences can affect both perceived value and consumer behaviour. What is more, --the atmosphere and ambience -- in general, by applying strategic sensory integration framework, the memorability of a visitor, and have an emotional impact on a fine dining experience. Furthermore, the researchers showed that despite the location of the restaurant the sensory rich environment with emotional engagement increases the chance of return to the same place as well as extend the dining duration.

Besides, the usage of storytelling and technology demonstrates how neuropsychological mechanisms are being used in more interesting way. As Gao and Krashes (2024) said in their research: "Consumption behaviors are deeply tied to environmental stimuli, suggesting that ethical design considerations are vital to avoid overconsumption while enhancing guest satisfaction".

2.2. Cost Of Guest Satisfaction

Sustainability now is an topic of an increasing concern, specifically in hospitality industry. Modern dining concepts currently focus not only on the quality of service and creative menu offers, but also on integrating sustainability integrations to highlight the social responsibility (Kim et al., 2023). As the standards and requirements are changing swiftly, the ongoing debate arises around the topic whether sustainability goals may be achieved at the cost of compromising guest satisfaction.

For example, in *Divine Dining Decisions* by Che Mohd Hashim et al. (2024) it is observed that Muslim millennials prioritize ethical conservations over sustainability practices, such as Halal authenticity, when choosing a restaurant. It shows that the guest satisfaction can be achieved by applying only ethical considerations, disregarding the sustainability practices. Also, Kim et al. (2023) found in their research that culturally resonant food and beverages increases the 'green' image and makes the perceived value appear stronger – this is an example of how design and visual presentation, explained on a deeper level, can serve ethical messaging. Both of the aforementioned examples are well illustrating and supporting the statement that by using ethical messaging rather than using superficial additions, the guest satisfaction can be brought to the next level. This statement is an underlining of the importance of ethical compliance when it comes to modern dining concepts.

Jose et al. (2025) stated that the consumers have been expressing preferences towards the aspect of transparency and responsibility in sourcing when selecting a dining outlet. This means that companies' honest and frank practices, like possibility for digital monitoring of animal welfare, impacts consumer attitudes to shift more towards ethical food consumption. Nonetheless, fine dining restaurants, in general, do not follow this trend and contrast in lack of such practices, leading to the lower satisfaction of the visitors and slower progress in creating the long-term link between the establishment and the guest, as now trust becomes a determinant factor in decision-making. Batat's (2021) research brought attention to this gap, which highlighted that the exclusivity and the indulgence provided in fine dining restaurants overshadows the fast growing customer demand for simple transparency. He discovered that modern clientele is becoming more and more conscious about not only about the meal at the moment, but about what has been with it before and what comes after, which leads to growing number of requests for ethical food sourcing and sustainable practices to be transparently showed during the dining experience.

However, what Huang et al. (2023) mentioned in their research is that high-end and fine dining restaurants, like Michelin Green Star nominees, despite aligning the mission and vision with the ethical standards, do not fail to still provide luxurious, unique, and tailored experiences, showcasing the proof or correlation between the two aspects. This was also underlined by Liu and Tse (2021) who found out in their

research that consumers' perceptions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in regard to health and well-being have a positive impact on the willingness to dine. The research states that if the restaurant shows that transparency in following the health practices and ethical values, it can result in getting better reviews and gain customer loyalty, even in competitive markets.

On the other hand, Mejjia and Wilson (2024) conducted their study based on the counterargument saying that most of the fine dining restaurants are willing to achieve higher guest reviews and get their loyalty, leaving behind the importance of ethical rules, like wastefulness or inequality in service environments. What is being caused in this case is the social unsustainability and labour exploitation. This insight starts a rethinking process of importance of restructuring the evaluation algorithm of guest satisfaction beyond perception, as the satisfaction alone is now considered a sufficient metric, and considering societal costs of fine dining restaurants.

Guachalla (2022) addresses the point that ethical and sustainable implementations in the hospitality industry are needed in order for restaurants to have a better approach to health, sustainability and social equity without leaving behind the innovation or creativity. His research describes a deeper approach for the restaurants to achieve guest satisfaction through understanding their values and mindsets. In addition, Tahir et al. (2022) stated that casual dining clientele often exhibits more environmentally conscious behaviours, compared to fine dining consumers. Their study shows that

people who are more interested in visiting fine dining establishments have higher expectations in food quality at the exact moment, due to the price difference factor, rather than the effects it can cause, hence leading to the point that restaurants are being more exposed to overconsumption patterns or unsustainable habits. This issue raises the question about the responsibility of high-end restaurants to promote more sustainable approach in their operation routine, because of the elevated guest expectations.

Yet, Liu et al. (2023) have their research based on Value-Attitude-Behaviour (VAB) model and applying it towards the finding that people tend to associate and identify themselves with the brands that reflect their values. The self-image congruity can be used by the restaurants to integrate more sustainable and ethical strategies without negatively affecting the brand image.

All these studies clearly demonstrate that modern dining concepts can deliver high levels of satisfaction without a sacrifice of ethical or sustainable practices, even though it is what is being faced now. Overall, the guest satisfaction and sustainability are not mutually exclusive, not leaving behind that the transparency and sustainability which appear to increase consumer trust in a restaurant brand as well as gain consumers loyalty and engagement.

With that in mind, guest satisfaction may decrease due to exposure of factors such as overconsumption and therefore, as alluded to by Mejia and Wilson (2024), navigating this balance requires process-driven leadership management style.

2.3. Implementation Of Sustainable Practices

The fast-growing trend of sustainability implementations in daily operations made the shareholders to rethink how they should organise their work operations. In order to balance their social responsibility and brand image the fine dining restaurants tend to implement more sustainability-oriented strategies in order to gain more innovative and ecological respective reputation. By achieving this, the consumer behaviour, operations and organisation's performance will be affected.

The research conducted by Mudana et al. (2024) in Bali together with stakeholders shows how Sofi System Methodology (SSM) was applied to create new ideas of a sustainable solution. These results have demonstrated how the combination of both creative thinking and social responsibility can create a truly sustainable culinary identity. Liu et al. (2022) explored this further through the five senses. They highlighted the importance of sensory immersion in the creation of experiences, drawing specific attention to the coexistence of sensory design, cultural authenticity, and sustainability. Although their research is mostly based on five senses and cultural diversity, there are still opportunities and already existing sustainable implementations. They describe the perfect balance between social responsibility to follow sustainable rules and neuropsychological mechanism.

Wei and Pujari (2024) mentioned that Green Innovation is also identified as Green Acquisition in their research, stating that this approach could enhance the performance

of the restaurant by adopting eco-friendly strategies. This approach was created in order to balance the environmental and economic outcomes in the operations. This idea is a part of concept development strategy that could be potentially aligned with sustainability without damaging the business.

Baby et al. (2024) proved that by promoting sustainability as a main element of dining experience could enhance the consumers loyalty and increase social responsibility. By applying cultural traditions in local restaurants, the place will be able to promote local identity. And as was stated above, people are more attracted to the place with clear vision – this serves as a great example of the existing practice of combining both concept and applying their use to create the balanced, creative and yet sustainable experience. This was further confirmed by Yarış and Yazıcıoğlu (2020), who stated that by applying eco-friendly practices such as waste reduction, energy efficiency and ethical sources are crucial to customer behavior and the alignment with neurophysiological principles.

Research by Ngo (2024) the concept of “ambidextrous green innovation” further emphasizes the importance of balancing new and existing sustainability innovations in the hospitality industry. His case study clearly highlights that when the restaurant is implementing both innovation and efficiency in green initiatives, it leads to positive change in organizational performance and brand reputation. It means that the sustainability and creativity could work together to enhance not only the guest

satisfaction, but also efficiency and performance of a property. This is supported by Montesdeoca-Calderón et al. (2024), who said that top management must implement the employees' trainings in sustainability and wood waste management to help them to understand the importance of these practices. Moreover, it increases the level of Sustainability-Oriented Service Innovation (SOSI) and enhances brand equity. Their research shows that good team of leaders with clear understanding of the situation together with appropriate company culture and competencies in sustainability could lead the restaurant to the success.

As mentioned by Khan et al. (2024) the sustainability practices are not only indicating social responsibility, but also a source of profit. By showing to the customers the transparency in logistic chain, waste management, etc., the restaurant could get more loyal customers and better operational outcomes. The company should integrate the sustainability practices in their DNA as well as promoting them at the same time.

Additionally, Maia et al. (2024) introduced insights from the circular economy, highlighting how waste management system and local supply chain integration could enhance restaurant models by making them more efficient and environmentally circular. Their study provides actionable pathways for concept developers seeking to merge creative menu design, local identity, and zero-waste practices.

Weijers et al. (2024) looked at how small changes to menus can encourage people to choose more sustainable foods, like vegetarian meals. They found that simple,

smart design tricks can help guide customers to make eco-friendly choices without making them feel pressured or less satisfied with their dining experience. This shows that creatively presenting food can also support environmental goals.

Overall, these studies demonstrate that both creative and sustainable restaurant concepts are not only possible, but increasingly popular in today's industry.

Ideas such as designing memorable dining experiences (Liu et al., 2022), integrating eco-friendly practices into daily operations (Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu, 2020), and training staff to support green initiatives (Montesdeoca-Calderón et al., 2024) are all demonstrations of how to effectively leverage this principle.

On top of that, bigger-picture planning (Mudana et al., 2024), smart menu design to influence choices (Weijers et al., 2024), and business strategies that support green innovation (Ngo, 2024; Wei & Pujari, 2024) further confirm this idea thus emphasizing its importance.

In short, restaurants can absolutely create experiences that are fun, unique, and not only less harmful, but even beneficial for the planet. In fact, being sustainable can actually boost how customers see the brand, improve reputation, and support long-term success. Moving forward, more research should look at how to apply these strategies across all types of restaurants—especially in casual and fast-food places, where sustainable practices might not be as common yet.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework

The Role Of Neuropsychological Responses
In Multisensory Dining Experiences

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Personal Creation

3. Methodology

The methodological framework is explained in great detail in the following chapter guiding the exploration into neuropsychological responses to multisensory dining. This chapter raises a specific focus on research approach, and design underpinning the study. Furthermore, it details the procedures for primary data collection, the techniques planned for data analysis, measures to ensure research quality, anticipated limitations, and crucial ethical considerations pertinent to the research aim and objectives.

3.1 Research Design and Approach

This research adopted a positivist philosophical stance, assuming an objective reality that can be observed and measured empirically (Park, 2020; Saunders et al., 2023, p. 148). This approach is suited to studying neuropsychological responses indirectly through measurable perceptual and behavioral proxies, seeking quantifiable patterns rather than subjective meanings often explored via interpretivism. Positivism aligns with the study's aim to quantify relationships between sensory inputs, perceived value, and consumption behaviours using numerical data. Its ontological stance posits that these phenomena exist independently, and epistemologically, knowledge is gained through objective measurement and statistical analysis.

This has been approached with a deductive research strategy, starting by using the theories obtained from the literature review to formulate testable hypotheses on the effects of multisensory dining (Thomas, 2022, p. 2). This then consisted of expanding the general theory to more channeled data collection and testing. That is suitable for examining the hypothesized links between sensory experience, value, and sustainability behaviors.

This study used a quantitative survey strategy within a single method framework. The choice of method is due to the need for standardized, numerical data that lends itself to statistical analysis identifying patterns across participants, examining relationships between variables, and addressing the research objectives and hypotheses (Khan et al., 2023, p. 122).

Qualitative methods were clearly less effective in measuring the extent and the strength of these relationships across the sample. The purpose of the research is to explain the connections between multisensory elements, value perception, and sustainability-related behaviors (Xiong, 2023). Whilst this is explanatory in nature, it incorporated descriptive elements when contextualizing the sample.

This study used a cross-sectional time frame, which means that data was gathered at one specific point to capture a momentary view of studied variables (Ghanad, 2023).

3.2 Data Collection

3.2.1 Population, Sampling Technique, and Sample

The target population consisted of consumers who occasionally dine out and have experienced or are interested in experiential/multisensory dining. No specific age range was selected in order to capture a broad spectrum of opinions. While the demographics were not an asked subject in the survey, the initial screening question ensures participants possess relevant context or interest regarding the study's core focus. Inclusion required confirming interest/experience via filtering question FQ1. Those uninterested in experiential dining were excluded.

Due to the lack of a defined sampling frame, non-probability sampling was employed. This was used mostly when referring to convenience and self-selection techniques (Stratton, 2021; Sirwan, 2024). Convenience sampling involved leveraging existing contacts, whilst self-selection was obtained through a publicly shared survey link on social media. This combined approach was a practical way of receiving data but greatly limited the ability to statistically generalize the findings as the sample might have not been fully representative (Venter & Mouton, 2022).

The study aimed for a sample size of approximately 50 respondents, considered feasible for this thesis' scope. The final achieved sample size and response rate are detailed in the results chapter. The limitations regarding

representativeness and statistical power due to the sampling method and modest sample size were acknowledged (Mattei, 2025)

3.2.2 Research Design and Collection Process

A structured, self-administered online questionnaire served as the primary data collection instrument. It was created based on findings made in literature review chapter (sensory experience, perceived value, sustainability behaviours) and research objectives, using newly created questions designed to quantitatively measure these constructs (Saunders et al., 2023, p. 160). These Likert scale items were specifically newly designed to operationalize and quantitatively measure the core constructs identified in the literature review and conceptual framework: Sensory Experience, Perceived Value, and Sustainable Behavior/Intentions. The questionnaire comprised four sections: introduction/ethics, a filtering question (FQ1) for eligibility, sensory experience assessment (5 Likert items), perceived value measurement (5 Likert items), and sustainability behaviour/intentions exploration (6 Likert items). The main instrument contained 16 questions, utilizing single-choice and 5-point Likert scales, a common method for efficiently interpreting attitudes and perceptions numerically.

Considerable thought had to be put into the filtering question as, given the narrow focus of the study, it was crucial to quickly exclude non-relevant respondents. The filtering question was as follows: "Thinking about dining out, which statement best

describes your experience with or interest in ‘experiential’ or ‘multisensory’ dining settings (e.g., restaurants focusing heavily on unique atmosphere, themed concepts, creative presentation, sound, scent, etc.)?”

This question served both as a brief introduction to the scope of the survey, and as a way of quickly excluding participants who cannot meaningfully answer the questions thus significantly maximizing the opportunity for accurate data collection.

Google Forms was used for survey creation and administration, offering accessibility and anonymity that may encourage more candid responses. The survey link was distributed via social media platforms (Instagram). Data collection was planned over approximately 3 weeks. A data requirement table can be found in Appendix B as well as the full survey text (Appendix C).

3.2.3 Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted to check for any modifications that may be required. The format of the pilot involved sending the survey to four people with varying levels of English language aptitude. This was done to check the clarity of both the introduction and the questions themselves. This was important given that the survey would ultimately be distributed to a large number of non-native English speakers. It was

also important to check that the survey could be meaningfully completed in the claimed 7–12-minute time frame.

Feedback from the four participants was collected and it was suggested to further simplify the language used in the questions as there was a risk of it being too advanced for the proposed sample. This feedback was subsequently incorporated into the final survey. This was helpful to confirm factors such as timing and reliability (Saunders et al., 2023, p. 548).

3.3 Data Analysis Methods

Data analysis was made using Google Sheets for initial data management (export, cleaning, organization) and descriptive statistics. This instrument was chosen due to its higher convenience compared to Microsoft Excel, as all numerical values were automatically transferred from the survey form, providing for less time-consuming and more sustainable analysis.

Analysis was conducted in two stages. Firstly, descriptive statistics (percentages) were computed and shown in bar charts as a summary of the sample characteristics and provide initial context regarding participant perceptions on key variables (Dehalwar, 2024, p. 214). Secondly, inferential statistics were used in order to test the hypothesis. Specifically, the core relationships of the hypothesis.

- **H₁₁**: Testing the relationship between Sensory Experience (SE) and Perceived Value (PV). The null hypothesis (H₀₁) suggests no significant relationship while the alternative (H₁₁) suggests a significant positive relationship.
- **H₁₂**: Testing the relationship between Sensory Experience (SE) and the Sustainability Behavior (SB) variable. The null hypothesis (H₀₂) posits no significant relationship, while the alternative (H₁₂) posits a significant positive relationship between SE and pro-sustainability intentions/behaviors.

The decision to reject or fail to reject the null hypotheses was based on the absolute majority principle, where the relationship was acknowledged if 70% of respondents or more chose option “Agree” or “Strongly Agree” respectively.

3.4 Validity and Reliability

Validity means to ensure the accuracy of the instrument in measuring the intended constructs (Quintão et al., 2022). Content validity is further enhanced by basing the questionnaire items in literature (Chapter 2). In doing this, relevance to the research objectives and hypotheses is ensured. This was crucially achieved by rewriting questions to meet the desired outcome based on feedback regarding participant understanding and perception of relevance (Quintão et al., 2022).

The feedback confirmed that the questions have been interpreted as intended. Construct validity is mainly addressed through operationalization, translating the

abstract theory of sensory experience, value perception, and sustainability behavior from literature into objective and clearly worded survey questions. This was achieved by using unambiguous language.

External validity, which is to say how findings can be generalized, is limited due to probability sampling and the modest sample size (Dehalwar, 2024, p.121).

Reliability concerns the consistency and stability of measurement. The pilot study will help to identify the confusing items, as well as clear instructions in an online questionnaire. The use of explicit potential answers such as 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree' for Likert scale points ensures consistency in interpretation across participants.

3.5 Limitations

Some methodological limitations are acknowledged (Saunders et al., 2023, p. 134). A limitation of using self-selection for the surveys is response bias. Given that this survey was published on a personal social media account, with a broad international following, there is the possibility of the exclusion of individuals lacking literacy in the English language. Measures were taken to ensure eligibility for the study, including a filtering question that clearly stated that participation was only for those either interested in or who have participated in experiential dining.

This became evident when reviewing the data as four participants answered no to the filtering question, therefore effectively excluding them from the research. This will be expanded further during the results and discussion. However, they continued despite this which, in future research, may require modifying the filtering question to be even more explicit; however, this is to be expected when taking a diverse sample.

Furthermore, this method allowed for limited control over the environment of respondents when answering the survey, which may have reduced their ability to properly concentrate when recalling very specific memories about their previous dining experiences.

A second limitation of this study is external validity. This is mainly due to a relatively small sample, without the use of different demographics within said sample. Whilst this at face value could impact the ability to generalize the research findings, it is important to note that this study focuses on an incredibly niche area of luxury hospitality. This is to say that the only participants who could answer the survey are those who both possess the economic resources to access these experiences, and those who have a deeper interest in the various components of fine dining. Therefore, external validity being low is to be expected given the overall scope of the research.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were strongly adhered to throughout the data collection process (Tom Lindemann & Häberlein, 2023). This was first achieved by emphasizing the principle of informed consent. Within the introduction of the survey, the study purpose was clearly outlined, voluntary participation, estimated completion time, and the measures taken to ensure anonymity and confidentiality were also disclosed. Additionally, the right to withdraw without consequence was clearly stated. Therefore, proceeding with the survey implied that the above-mentioned criteria were met (Tripathi & Chaturvedi, 2023).

Anonymity was confirmed by virtue of not asking for any personal details e.g. names, email addresses and phone numbers.

Confidentiality was protected through both the above and the methods for data aggregation, ensuring that individual responses could not be traced to participants.

Maintaining data security was straightforward given the lack of personal information, however the data was secured by password only available to the researcher and the tutor and was used only for the purpose of this thesis and the fulfillment of the course requirements (Tom Lindemann & Häberlein, 2023).

Any potential harm was avoided given the topics of the questions were non-sensitive. All questions were phrased neutrally to avoid leading or causing distress to participants. The adherence to ethical guidelines was carefully observed during the

design and execution of the research. The principles of integrity commanded both an honest and transparent analysis and reporting of findings, importantly, whether they support the initial hypotheses or not (Tripathi & Chaturvedi, 2023).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

The following section aims to discuss the results of primary data collection and to analyse the previously developed hypotheses to outline whether there is a significant relationship between variables or not. Data was collected via an online survey (Google Forms), which after the dedicated timeframe was answered by 66 participants. There were 4 respondents who selected the option that implied the lack of interest in the research topic, hence, should have withdrawn. However, the decision was made to still consider them, as it provides a broader overview.

4.1.2 The role of a filtering question

At the beginning of the survey the filtering question segmented respondents by their level of interest and exposure to the topic of research. This helped to draw a more relevant study out of the general population as the nature of multisensory dining is niche.

Results showed that 37.9% of participants frequently seek out unique dining settings, while 39.4% indicated their occasional exposure to multisensory experiences. 16.7% of respondents chose an option “I haven’t tried such settings yet, but I am interested in experiencing them”, which reveals potential openness. Lastly, only 6.1% chose an option that implied withdrawing from continuing the survey, as those participants expressed interest in solely traditional dining settings.

Based on the received results, a core sample was framed out of the participants who chose the first two options (77.3%). The remaining data was still considered as an indicator of innovation responsiveness.

Thinking about dining out, which statement best describes your experience with or interest in 'experiential' or 'multisensory' dining settings (e.g., restaurants focusing heavily on unique atmosphere, themed concepts, creative presentation, sound, scent, etc.)?

[Копировать диаграмму](#)

66 ответов

Figure 2. Filtering Question

4.2. Results and Discussions: Sensory Experience

The visual presentation of dishes affected my perception of taste.

66 ответов

Figure 3. Sensory Experience Q1

All of the Likert-scale items in the section “Sensory Experience” were aimed to show whether stimulation of 5 human senses has an influence on guest’s meal experience. The first question was focused on evaluating the correlation between visual presentation of dishes and perception of taste. Results show that 36.4% strongly agree with that idea, while 48.5% also expressed acknowledgement of that factor by selecting the “Agree” option. Only 10.6% of respondents remained neutral, and 4.5% (3 respondents) showed their disagreement with the sentence.

What can be concluded from that data, as majority agreed with the given sentence, is that visual presentation is essential in shaping flavour perception, aligned with the findings of Youssef and Spence (2023) who mentioned that what is seen on the plate can build up a higher emotional resonance even before eating the food served.

The atmosphere of the restaurant (music, lighting, smells) enhanced my dining experience.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 4. Sensory Experience Q2

The second question was focused on the atmosphere of the restaurant. The survey results show that majority of participants share the agreement on that statement with 63.6% choosing “Strongly Agree” option and 31.8% choosing “Agree”.

As only the minority of participants (3%) expressed a disagreement with the statement, a strong verdict that external ambient factors enrich guest experience and elevate the quality of consumed meal was reached. This data clearly supports the findings made by Spence (2021), who discussed in detail the importance of olfactory cues and that pleasant odor in the establishment elevate the satisfaction rate of the guests.

The meal engaged (or would engage) multiple senses (sight, sound, smell, touch, taste) in a unique way.

66 ответов

Figure 5. Sensory Experience Q3

This Likert-scale item focused on identifying whether the idea of multisensory dining can promote unique experiences and feelings. 42.4% strongly agreed and 37.9% agreed with that, while 15.2% decided to remain neutral.

A large percent of agreement and a minor portion of disagreeing participants (4.5% in total) strongly reflects the idea of the meal, that engages multiple senses can be considered unique.

This data strongly supports the fact that multisensory dining generates eccentric, long-lasting memories by evoking unique feelings, corresponding with the experiment discussed by Rottigni & Spence (2024), where guests, who were exposed to external stimulations of senses combined with extraordinary storytelling were reported to cry during the meal, meaning that powerful emotions were evoked.

The physical textures of the space (e.g., furniture, tableware) influenced how I experienced the meal.

64 ответа

Figure 6. Sensory Experience Q4

On the contrary to the previous questions, this Likert-scale item aimed at looking into the correlation between physical stimuli, (e.g., furniture, tableware) and the meal experience.

The equal amount of opinions was spread between “Strongly Agree” and “Agree”, reaching a point of 35.9% each, while 6 respondents (9.4%) did not confirm the relationship between those variables. 18.8% remained neutral.

Even though the agreement rate is slightly less in this question rather than in previous ones, the results still show that more than 70% of respondents, hence, majority, confirm that tactility has a meaningful impact on influencing the dining experience. Those findings accord with ideas of Yuan et al. (2022), stating that environmental design and table layout increases the level of mental connection with the dining space.

Aromas in the dining space shaped my appetite and emotional state, even before eating.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 7. Sensory Experience Q5

This Likert scale question was taken to capture any olfactory ambience in the dining area that might have affected the participants' appetite and emotion (mood) before starting to eat. The response profile is robust, with 45.5% strongly agreeing and 34.8% agreeing, so that approximately four out of every five participants were willing to identify the emotional and biophysical preservice impact of odor. 12.1% of them, on the other hand, were neutral, while a small percentage disagreed (6.1%) or strongly disagreed (1.5%).

These results support the importance of olfactory cues in anticipation of dining as demonstrated in the study by Spence (2021), addressing the powerful role of olfaction as a multisensory modulator of mood, memory, and eating behavior.

4.3. Results and Discussion: Perceived Value

I would recommend this place not for the food alone but for how it made me feel.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 8. Perceived Value Q1

The question aimed to find out by how much customers would recommend a restaurant not just on culinary merit, but by how the experience made them feel.

This chart shows that 45.5% of participants would strongly recommend a restaurant based on how it makes them feel. 37.9% of people agree with the statement. On the contrary, 3% of participants strongly disagree with the statement and 13.6% remain neutral.

These results are strongly in line with literature cited for Objective 2, including Liu et al. (2023) and Huang et al. (2023) argued that emotional attachment (which could be influenced by multisensory cues such as service interaction) are crucial to both creating perceived value as well as guiding future behavioral intentions such as to word-of-mouth. The results are also consistent with the contention of Jose et al.

(2025) that the bonding of the customer is moving to emotional appeal rather than just satisfaction from the product.

Considering the overall experience, it felt (or would feel) like good value for the money.

66 ответов

Figure 9. Perceived Value Q2

This question seeks to obtain value perception after having experienced an innovative dining setting. 47% of respondents either agreed or strongly agreed with the statement, aggregating 94% of the sample. By contrast, 4.5% were indifferent and 1.5% disagreed with the statement.

These results indicate that most participants thought it was worthwhile to have a multisensory dining experience, supporting the insights of reviewed literature such as findings made by Tsaur & Lo (2020) and Liu et al. (2023), showing that stimulating multiple senses increases the perceived value to customers and their overall satisfaction with dining.

The dining experience created (or would create) a memorable impression.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 10. Perceived Value Q3

This chart shows the extent to which a multisensory dining experience would create a memorable impression amongst customers. What was found is that 66.7% of respondents strongly agree, 30.3% agree, 3% are neutral, and there was no disagreement.

It can be concluded from this data that the perception is that a multisensory dining experience would create a memorable impression. These findings align with the work of Velasco et al. (2024), who suggested that effective memory encoding and consumer engagement hinge on how well our senses work together. Additionally, as Spence (2020) points out, sensory elements like music, scents, and lighting come together to create emotionally rich, immersive experiences that are more likely to be remembered. All these studies support the notion that engaging our senses

enhances our lasting memories of a meal, turning it from just food into a memorable event.

I would return to such an experience even at a premium price point.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 11. Perceived Value Q4

The statement asks participants to reflect on whether they would return to such an experience regardless of a high price point. 43.9% strongly agree, 30.3% agree, however, 16.7% are neutral and 9.1% either strongly disagree or agree. This shows that a vast majority of participants would return to such an experience regardless of the price point.

Whilst on the one hand it shows that there is desirability and customer loyalty associated with these experiences, as the total agreement rate reached the point of more than 70% (validating the absolute majority principle). On the other hand, the expressed neutrality and albeit small number of people who disagree show that there

might need to be work done to increase this emotional connection between restaurants and customers.

This duality highlights some important insights from the literature, showing that there's a real chance to reach out to customers who are still on the fence. Huang et al. (2023) point out that sensory-driven culinary tourism experiences can really enhance consumer satisfaction and perceived value, especially when these experiences tap into emotional and cultural connections.

In the same line, Jose et al. (2025) indicate that customer loyalty in sensory dining does not only merely draw out sensorial stimulation, but also depends on the meaningful, personal relationship. The data would seem to indicate that companies should, instead of the appealing multisensory angles, play up the emotional engagement, cultural storytelling, and memories of experience to win over the former group of not yet convinced clients, increasing not only their perceived value but also likelihood of return.

The multisensory elements made the experience feel worth more than a standard fine-dining meal.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 12. Perceived Value Q5

The above statement aims to specify what about a dining experience leads to a supposed increased value perception. 48.5% of participants strongly agree, 39.4% agree, 7.6% remain neutral, and 4.5% either disagree or strongly disagree with the statement. The conclusion drawn from this is that for 87.9% of participants, multisensory elements are not only important but a defining factor in the elevation of an already high-end experience. One could argue that given eligibility for the survey is contingent upon having experienced multisensory dining, or at least being interested by it, it stands to reason that they would see the value in it above a standard fine-dining meal.

While the reviewed previously literature did not specifically focus on comparing fine dining with multisensory dining experiences, the received data unfolds an exciting prospect for future research. It highlights how emotional connection could potentially play as a key factor in driving customer loyalty and perceived value, setting apart traditional fine dining from the more immersive, multisensory experiences.

4.4. Results and Discussion: Sustainability Behaviour and Intentions

I consumed more than I needed due to the emotionally stimulating setting.

66 ответов

Figure 13. Sustainability Behavior Q1

This statement asks the participants to reflect on whether the environment of the restaurant stimulates overconsumption. 30.3% strongly agree, 24.2% agree, 24.2% are neutral, 16.7% disagree, and 4.5% strongly disagree. This result strongly suggests that when people go to a dining establishment, they are far more likely to overconsume. This is to be expected as most people go to a restaurant of this level when celebrating and therefore overindulgence is part of the experience. However, 45.4% of respondents vary from neutrality to disagreement, which suggests that, whilst there is an observable pattern, there is still disagreement on the issue.

This perspective is also shared by Malcman et al. (2024) who demonstrated that ambient factors are capable of affecting food liking. Their findings are that sensory

atmospheres represent cues for behavior and that crossmodal design can influence consumption in the absence of diner awareness.

Consistent with this idea, Gao & Krashes (2024) further provide neurophysiological evidence that brainstem neurons located in the nucleus of the solitary tract (NTS) control feeding and satiety and are responsive to multi-modal sensory cues. They stress that the PRLH-GCG neurons communicate satiation by reducing the feeding lick rate and stamps duration irrespective of meal size, but that this process is able to be overturned by environmental food sensory information. That would suggest that it might be that guests are eating more than they normally would as a result of multisensory dining disrupting normal satiety signals, so even once they're full they would continue to eat.

Taken together, these findings reveal the unethical part of sensory hospitality: while it serves to enhance guest experience, it can also inadvertently hinder the body's natural regulation of itself.

I rarely question sustainability claims (e.g., single-use decor, and imported ingredients) when I'm emotionally engaged by the experience

66 ответов

Figure 14. Sustainability Behavior Q2

This is a critical question to ask as a follow-up to the above, as it shows how typically fine-dining consumers question the claims being made by restaurants. 50% strongly agree, 21.2% agree, 13.6% are neutral, and a combined 15.1% of participants either disagree or strongly disagree. This clearly shows that in the high-end dining sector, consumers do not prioritize sustainability as they take claims by restaurants at face value and do not consider them further if there is an emotional connection.

Observation here recalls the central concern identified in literature review:

campaigners against unethical treatment of animals face a problem of emotionally involving dining experiences outweighing the rational consciousness of ethical

conduct. While nowhere does any of the reviewed literature ever mention that

consumers completely throw out sustainability considerations when dining in an

immersive environment, the depicted behaviour does rather imply that a gap exists.

As it has been explained in research works such as in one by Tahir et al. (2022), fine dining patrons are myopic in that they care mostly just about immediate quality and hedonism, and to a lesser extent, the larger moral picture. It is also the case, as Mejia and Wilson (2024) note, where guest satisfaction at the high-end of the market may come before sustainability as luxurious hospitality is presented in an immersive, emotionally organized manner that is resistant to cognitive engagement with ethical matters.

Instead of complaining about the imported ingredients, or a single-use décor, visitors seem to assume that it's just part of the overall luxury story. This only underscores the necessity for restaurants to make sustainability part of their model of perception as well as their operating model, make it visible and emotionally compelling, rather than expecting customers to do the homework on it themselves.

I am less focused on mindful consumption (e.g., finishing everything, avoiding waste) when I'm highly engaged by a unique dining experience.

66 ответов

Figure 15. Sustainability Behavior Q3

This statement is designed to see if consumers are mindful of their consumption habits when immersed in a unique dining experience. 36.4% strongly agree, 28.8% agree, 12.1% are neutral, and an aggregate 19.7% disagree.

Combined with the results from the prior question, this data provides even more proof to the idea that the more emotion is involved in the dining experience, the less critical and mindful decisions regarding consumption are made. Same as the data in the previous question, the results align with findings of Tahir et al. (2022), stating that sustainability is not being top priority among fine dining consumers, compared to casual diners. Moreover, Mejia and Wilson (2024) also mentioned that ethical awareness is being less acclaimed when guest satisfaction becomes the dominant goal, which is a tendency that immersive dining settings may unintentionally amplify.

I trust the aesthetic of high-end restaurants to imply responsible practices, even without proof.

66 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 16. Sustainability Behavior Q4

This aim of this question was to explore whether consumers associate the aesthetics of high-end restaurants with responsible and ethical practices, even with zero proof. A total of 77.2% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed, while only 15.1% strongly disagreed or disagreed (combined).

From that data a conclusion can be made that a strong trend to associate creative and luxurious dining environments with automatic ethical behaviour is arising. This tie proposes an idea that thorough storytelling can be misused to conceal the actual sustainability performance of a restaurant. Because of the fact that consumers do not ask for verification, an issue of blind trust might arise, that may lead to unconscious support of unsustainable initiatives.

Nevertheless, as the literature suggests, this conflict could also indicate potential. Liu et al. (2022) and Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu (2020) noted that the increasing amount of implemented sustainable practices in dining is now shifting from being a unique selling point to a bare minimum, an expectation, especially in experiential and fine dining settings. Because the chain of restaurants that incorporate the idea of sustainability with a multisensory experience is increasing, the uncritical consumers trust could become a force contributing to the advancement of an ethical behavior in the immersive dining environments. This point illustrates the double-edged sword of aesthetic trust: although it may obfuscate transparency, it also demonstrates that

there is ever-increasing the expectation that immersive dining is sustainable by default.

Ethical transparency (e.g., showing food waste levels, local sourcing proof) would enhance rather than spoil my dining experience.

65 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 17. Sustainability Behavior Q5

This question aimed to evaluate if promoting ethical transparency, like sharing food waste levels and providing guests with local sourcing proof would make an experience more valuable and even enjoyable, rather than spoiling it. A total of 70.8% agreed/strongly agreed and 16.9% disagreed, while 12.3% remained neutral. These findings contrast with previous question results in which consumers were evidenced to have cursory examination towards sustainability claims. The fact that respondents previously were willing to implicitly trust the ethical standards of restaurants, and yet here feel that transparency would not be an intrusive change, is a proof of the concept -- it's not unwanted on the contrary. This would indicate that the absence of questioning is not about a denial of sustainability values, but rather

an emotional displacement or aesthetic trust. As Khan et al. (2024) and Ngo (2024) emphasise, the hospitality sector is one of the major green innovators mostly for performance and brand value reasons rather than solely ethical. With that in mind, a reference to the study of Weijers et al. (2024) can be made. What is demonstrated in the study is that if small sustainability triggers would be integrated into design of the dining environment, the guest satisfaction would not be compromised. Those findings reveal the potential: for as much as emotional immersion may seem to reduce critical thinking at the onset, it does not necessarily preclude guests from valuing, and even demanding sustainable transparency.

I would be more impressed if a restaurant created a luxurious, emotional experience without harming the planet.

64 ответа

Figure 18. Sustainability Behavior Q6

The last question in the survey aimed to evaluate the impact of implementing sustainable initiatives on the appeal of dining environments to clients – if it will be weakened or strengthened. The results show that 45.3% strongly agree and another

21.9% agreeing, concluding to the fact that 67.2% of respondents would be more impressed by a concept that incorporates satisfaction from a luxurious experience with environmental responsibility. Even though the agreement rate did not reach the desired 70% to be signified as absolute majority, a relatively low percentage of disagreement with the statement (10.9%) could be an opposing factor, exposing growing potential.

This data states that sustainability, when paired with creativity, is now being more seen as a value enhancing instrument, rather than a barrier. It aligns well with what Yariş and Yazıcıoğlu (2020) found in their study: ethical practices, when being thoughtfully integrated into restaurant's operations, are acting as an elevator for the client perception. Moreover, Ngo (2024) researched that there is a positive response from the guests on green innovations, a practice where the experience is benefiting from sustainability.

And the numbers here suggest that, not only are consumers willing to accept this mix but that they actively reward it with praise. Guachalla (2022) however highlighted some existing hospitality models to show that the combination of these services is possible, especially with sustainability is being embedded in storytelling and design. These results confirm the current change in the industry and propose new dining concepts should still exploit sustainability as a catalyst of multisensory innovation.

4.5. Hypothesis Discussion

4.5.1. Sensory Experience and Perceived Value

The results from the collected data for the Sensory Experience (SEQ1–SEQ5) and Perceived Value (PVQ1–PVQ5) question sections can be used as a proof for positive correlation between the two variables. In All five SE questions 70% or more of respondents selected “Agree” or “Strongly Agree” options, which aligns with an absolute majority principle, stating the fact that multisensory stimuli has a positive effect on dining experience. A similar trend can be observed in the PV section as well. For instance, 94% of respondents agreed that a multisensory experience was a great value of money (PVQ2), and 74.2% said that they would return even if the price is higher (PVQ4). These rates indicate that perceived value is rising, thus, being one of the things that are positively influenced by multisensory stimuli.

4.5.1.2. Conclusion

The null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected.

The alternative hypothesis (H_{11}) is accepted: there is a significant positive relationship between Sensory Experience and Perceived Value.

4.5.2. Sensory Experience and Sustainable Behaviour and Intentions

In contrast with the aforementioned compared variables, the relationship between sensory experience and sustainable behavior is more complex and multifaceted. On

one hand, first three of sustainability behavior questions (SBQ1–SBQ3) show mixed results, indicating that multisensory dining settings in fact promote unethical practices (overconsumption, blind trust), therefore, it can be a solid argument for rejecting the statement about strong positive relationship.

However, upon further analysis made by later questions (SBQ4–SBQ6), it was found that participants would favorably react to integrating the sustainable practices, making the fact of steadily rising potential for balancing creativity and environmental responsibility valid.

For instance, 70.8% agreed that ethical transparency would enhance dining (SBQ5), and 67.2% said they'd be more impressed by sustainable luxury (SBQ6). Although a few items slightly missed the 70% threshold, the cumulative trend strongly supports a link between sensory design and pro-sustainability attitudes when design is value-aligned, even if now it is on its early stages.

4.5.2.2. Conclusion

The null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected.

The alternative hypothesis (H_{12}) is accepted: there is a significant positive relationship between Sensory Experience and pro-sustainability intentions/behaviours, especially when sustainability is communicated emotionally and aesthetically.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary and Relevance of the Findings

This part is the final one in the study and is dedicated to review the main findings made, reflecting on practical and theoretical implications of the research to determine whether aim and objectives were achieved. Additionally, the recommendations to hospitality practitioners and for the further research were made at the end of the chapter.

The aim of this thesis was to examine neuropsychological reactions to meal experience and how they are relevant to two fundamental aspects: the perceived value and environmental sustainable behaviour. Particularly, the main focus was on identifying whether emotionally and sensorily appealing restaurant settings could foster not only higher customer satisfaction but also more pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors.

To address this aim, the research was guided by three objectives:

1. To identify and observe patterns of neuropsychological effects of unconventional dining on perceived value and consumption behaviour.
2. To assess if modern dining concepts provide guest satisfaction at the cost of unethical and unsustainable practices.
3. To evaluate existing concept development strategies for balancing creativity in dining and environmental responsibility.

The study involved a quantitative survey that targeted a sample of 66 respondents and applied a Likert-scale to measure the respondents' thinking on three segments related to the research rationale. A framework from existing literature of high-end multisensory dining was developed that reflected the perceptions and behavior of consumers within the study while capturing their perceptions and behavior.

5.2 Objective-by-Objective Evaluation

Objective 1: Multisensory Design and Perceived Value

The purpose of first objective was to explore if a thoroughly designed sensory environment in a dining space contributes somehow to the overall dining experience.

From the results of the survey the conclusion was made that over 70% of respondents agreed that immersive elements such as storytelling, music, odor, etc., strongly influence their perception of the meal. These experiences were described as memorable, enjoyable and a good value of money spent by respondents.

These results are consistent with previous research that highlighted the importance of sensory congruence in luxury encounters. The null hypothesis (H_{01}) that sensory design has no significant effect on perceived value and guest experience was thus rejected. The second alternative hypothesis (H_{11}) was accepted (significant positive correlation).

Conclusion: Objective 1 was achieved. The findings prove that the use of a multisensory space and stimuli contributes attractively to increase the perceived value by the guests and enhance general perception. Thus, the concept of experiential design is a strategic tool for the development of value in hospitality.

Objective 2: Guest Satisfaction VS Ethical Trade-offs

This objective investigated the idea of whether contemporary multisensory dining concepts deliver guest satisfaction while overlooking sustainability and ethical

considerations. Survey results confirmed that clients blindly automatically link luxury and creativity with to credibility, without empirical evidence of responsible practices. As the data shows, 77.2% of participants agreed that the aesthetics of high-end restaurants seem to already imply the usage of ethical standards, while others did not actively question sustainability claims when emotionally engaged. These findings imply that sensory satisfaction has the potential power to hide unethical features, not because guests are rejecting sustainability, but simply because in fully immersive environments, critical analysis lapses.

This observation is in accordance with what have been reported by Tahir et al. (2022) and Mejia & Wilson (2024) who found that, in the immersive setting, sustainability is frequently subordinated to guest satisfaction. But there's also a silver lining: ethical transparency is not a restraint. According to the data, 70.8% said that ethical proof would increase their enjoyment. So, satisfaction and ethics are not mutually exclusive, however, the correlation can be achieved by promoting ethical messaging to fit with the sensory journey.

Conclusion: Objective 2 was achieved. The findings show that guest satisfaction can promote unsustainable practices implicitly, but also point to where ethical concerns can be integrated creatively.

Objective 3: Aesthetic Trust and Sustainability Risk

The aim of the third objective was to evaluate existing concept development strategies in fine dining and assess how effectively they balance sensory creativity with environmental standards. The strong support of that statement was provided by the data as a major part of respondents expressed the higher level of impression from a dining experience that is both, emotionally stimulating and sustainable.

Moreover, in contrast with priorly discussed passive trust trend, respondents embraced the idea that showing sustainability does not lessen the experience if communicated well.

These observations are also supported by Guachalla (2022) who has uncovered working models of restaurants that already combine multisensory innovation with ethical action. So did Yarış and Yazıcıoğlu (2020), and Ngo (2024), pointing out that sustainability has become more of the norm than a competitive edge in design.

Current data supports this trajectory — guests seem to be responsive to innovation, as it also brings the feeling of responsibility.

Conclusion: Objective 3 was fully achieved. The data confirms that creative and ethical strategies are not opposed, on the contrary, dining spaces restaurants can, and increasingly should, pursue both simultaneously in future concept development, as what is being done now shows significant results.

5.3. “So What?”

This study adds to a global understanding of hospitality theory by advancing the proposition that hedonic environments influence not only satisfaction, but also ethical perceptions. In reality, it shows that:

- Guests don't argue sustainability – they just simply don't notice it unless it's well integrated.
- The aesthetic trust is a real phenomenon that is powerful enough to do both: outstand and promote ethical considerations.
- Conscious and thorough design is more than just aesthetics, as it acts as a tool to influence behavior, attention patterns and reshape values.

After all, restaurants do more than just serve food. They act as institutions in which values and emotions are aroused and beliefs are reinforced or even changed. If this fact is well-acknowledged, then there is an understanding of what it takes to create experiences that are not just impressive in the moment, but also sustainably influential.

5.4. Recommendations for Hospitality Practitioners

1. **Infuse Ambience Design With Sensory Elements**

Leverage color, material, storytelling and what I call service rituals to create an air of sustainability that is intuitive, not instructional.

2. Integrate Ethical Beliefs In An Employee Training Plan

As any experience, especially immersive, is curated by staff, empowering communication about sustainability can boost a service quality and awareness level .

3. Promote Transparency While Preserving The Magic

Reveal ethical practices like proof of local sourcing or waste reduction index in immersive way, through creative menus or interactive storytelling rather than moralising signs.

4. Use The 'Blind Trust' Fairly

Aligning expectations of guests with reality of followed ethical practices can be used as a great tool to decrease the level of greenwashing and build strong relationship with consumers.

5.5. Recommendations for Future Research

With all the findings made in the study, several recommendations can be outlined for the further research:

- To achieve more thorough, real-life based results, next studies can include measuring changes in behaviour during the multisensory dining experience through an experiment done in live dining settings. This would help to fill the gap between intention and action.
- The further research can also look deeper on the cross-generational patterns, namely identifying if Baby Boomers have different perception of multisensory dining than Generation Z. This would also enrich the research with a broader data.
- Proceeding with adding the external validity to the research, a cultural aspect can also be recommended to be considered to evaluate if the data would differ based on the origin or place of residence of the respondents. This can also be used to identify prospective markets for such establishments and tilt the study to more economic-oriented prism.
- To put the study on a more practical and scientific scope, neurophysiological tools, like brain-imaging, could be used to explain how multisensory dining literally shapes ethical processing with a physical rather than just intangible proof.

5.6. Final Thoughts

This study adds to the increasing interest in developing emotionally compelling, morally sound hospitality experiences. As restaurants continue to become more immersive, what gets served to guests is not being the only one part of the equation anymore — how guests feel, what they remember, what they take away and what they consider to be a part of themselves are now the new variables. This observation is serving as a foundational step to the topic of growing importance – the future of sustainable dining.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Literature Synthesis

Objective	Author(s)	Article title	Keywords	Methodology
Objective 1				
1	Youssef, J., & Spence, C. (2023)	Gastromotive dining: Using experiential multisensory dining to engage customers	Experiential marketing, Consumer experiences, Experience design, Dining experiences, Modernist cuisine	No data was used for the research described in the article.
1	Spence, C. (2020)	Using Ambient Scent to Enhance Well-Being in the Multisensory Built Environment	Smell, scent, built environment, multisensory, malodor, well-being, sensehacking	Systematic Literature Review
1	Velasco, C., Vargas, J., & Petit, O. (2024)	Multisensory experiences and technology in the context of wine experiences	Multisensory, technologies, wine, experiences	Systematic Literature Review
1	Yuan, J. J., Bauman, M. J., Ferns, B. H., Ebrahimzadeh, M., & Alshiha, A. A. (2022).	Restaurant Dining Environment, Restaurant Formality and Dining Involvement in the Context of Memorable Dining Experiences (Mdes)	Restaurant dining environment, memorable dining experiences, restaurant dining involvement, restaurant formality, measurement models	Quantitative method: online surveys, 282 responses

1	Kleinhans, E. H., Van Heerden, C. H., & Kleynhans, I. C. (2021)	Making “Sense” of the Middle of the Pyramid Consumer’s Dining Experience	Dining experience stimuli, multi-sensory stimuli, middle of the pyramid (MOP) consumers	Qualitative and quantitative method: literature review, consumer interviews, and structured questionnaires distributed to MOP consumers
1	Rottigni, F., & Spence, C. (2024)	Crying over food: An extraordinary response to a multisensory eating experience	Crying, Multisensory, Visceral, Embodied cognition, Food Nostalgia	Narrative literature review
1	Malcman, M., Azar, O. H., Shavit, T., & Rosenboim, M. (2024)	How Does Background Music Affect Dining Duration, Tips and Bill Amounts in Restaurants? A Field Experiment	Music tempo, restaurants, tips, field experiment, background music	Quantitative method: experimental research, 202 participants
1	Gao, C., & Krashes, M. J. (2024).	Neuroscience of eating: Pace and portion control	Neuroscience of eating, Satiety, Feeding behavior, Nucleus of the solitary tract (NTS), PRLH and GCG neurons, In vivo calcium imaging, Optogenetics, Multisensory feedback, Portion control, Appetite regulation	Quantitative method: experimental neuroscience methods
1	Chen, Y., Tsui, P., Chen, H., Tseng, H., & Lee, C. (2020)	A dining table without food: the floral experience at ethnic fine	Environment, tourist experience	Quantitative method: sample was developed using tablet computers to simulate flower

		dining restaurants		arrangements in restaurants. The research tools included a floral style preference scale and a tourist floral experience scale.
1	Tsaur, S., & Lo, P. (2020)	Measuring memorable dining experiences and related emotions in fine dining restaurants	Memorable dining experience; emotion; restaurant attribute; scale development; fine dining restaurant	Quantitative method: 393 valid responses

Objective 2

2	Che Mohd Hashim, A. J., Nazri, M. A., Aziz, S. A., Seman, J. A., & Majid, M. bin. (2024)	Divine Dining Decisions: Unveiling the Influences on Concept Restaurant Choices among Urban Muslim Millennials' Visit Intention	Spiritual intelligence, spiritual congruence, perceived price, Halal food & beverages, facilities and physical environment	Quantitative method: questionnaire, 150 responses
2	Kim, E. J., Kim, E. L., Kim, M., & Tang, J. (2023)	The matching effect of local food and color on ethical dining behaviors: the roles of credibility and green image	Matching effect, Marketing message, Sustainability, Local food, Color psychology, Perceived credibility	Two experimental studies were conducted. Study 1 used a 2 food source (non-sustainable vs sustainable) 2 color consistency (inconsistent vs consistent) factorial design (n = 231). Study 2 used a 2 food origin (world-famous vs locally renowned) 2 color consistency (inconsistent vs consistent) factorial design (n = 220).

2	Jose, H., Jackson, E. L., Duong, P., & Sung, B. (2025)	Ethical food consumption in the digital age: Consumer attitudes towards digitally monitored animal welfare in pork products finance decisions?	Customer perception, Fine dining, Experience marketing, Service innovation	Qualitative method: 20 interviews
2	Batat, W. (2021)	Consumers' perceptions of food ethics in luxury dining	Qualitative research, Corporate social responsibility, Sustainability, Hospitality, Luxury dining, Food ethics, Michelin-starred restaurants, Luxury gastronomy, French food culture, Consumer	Qualitative method: 35 participants
2	Huang, Y., Hall, C. M., & Chen, N. (2023)	The sustainability characteristics of Michelin Green Star Restaurants	Sustainable restaurants, Michelin guide, fine-dining restaurant, food system, sustainable food service practices	Systematic literature review and conceptual analysis
2	Liu, P., & Tse, E. C. (2021)	The Impact of Perceived Corporate Social Responsibility on Dining Intention in US Restaurants:	Corporate social responsibility, consumers' health, restaurants, dining intention, satisfaction	Quantitative methods: 414 respondents

		Focusing on Customers' Health		
2	Mejia, C., & Wilson, K. (2024)	Coming to terms with a socially unsustainable fine dining business model	Foodscape, Critical discourse analysis, Social equity, Restaurants, Celebrity chef, Michelin guide, Noma	Critical discourse analysis to inductively analyze 91 source documents retrieved through a lexical database search. The analysis yielded five overarching themes and six subthemes.
2	Guachalla, A. (2022)	Hospitality futures: Towards a sustainable, healthier and ethical way of catering	Sustainability, health, ethics, plant-based, veganism, catering operations	Systematic literature review
2	Tahir, F., Haq, J. U., Saleem, A., Akhtar, N., & Bonn, M. A. (2022).	Diner's Sustainable Behavior: Differences between Sustainable Behaviors of Casual and Fine Dining Consumers	Diner sustainable behavior, food surplus, feeling guilt, attitude, loyalty	Quantitative method: analysis using a mixed-method approach
2	Liu, S., Li, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2023)	Sustainable Operation of Fine-Dining Restaurants: Antecedents and Consequences of Customers' Self-Image Congruity at a Cantonese	Fine-dining restaurant, value-attitude-behavior framework, self-congruity theory, generational theory, perceived quality, willingness to pay a price premium	Quantitative method: questionnaire, Likert-scale items

		Michelin-Starred Restaurant Based on the Value-Attitude-Behavior Model		
Objective 3				
3	Mudana, I. G., Wijaya, I. N. C., Ginaya, I. G., & Gusman, D. (2024)	Application of Soft Systems Methodology Approach to Find Sustainable Gastronomic Solutions in Bali, Indonesia	Soft Systems Methodology, gastronomy tourism, Balinese cuisine	Systematic literature review
3	Liu, C., Wang, Y., Kuo, T. M., Chen, H., & Tsui, C. (2022)	Memorable dining experiences with five senses: Conceptualization and scale development	Memorable experience, five senses, restaurant, sensory marketing, scale development	Quantitative method: utilizing secondary data
3	Wei, Y., & Pujari, D. (2024)	Drivers of green innovation and green acquisition: empirical evidence from the food and beverage industry	Environmental regulation, media attention, top management, green innovation	The research model used secondary data based on 1,565 firm-year observations in the beverage and food industry in the US. The two-stage control function approach was used for data analysis.
3	Baby, J., Barbieri, C., & Knollenberg, W. (2024)	Creative Tourism: An Umbrella for Agrifood Travel Experiences?	Agritourism, craft beverage tourism, creativity, culinary tourism, travel scenario	Quantitative method, survey, 1019 responses
3	Yarış, A., &	Intentions to	Eco-friendly	Mixed-methods approach

	Yaziciođlu, İ. (2020)	Adopt Eco-friendly Practices in Restaurant Operations	practice, eco-innovation diffusion, eco- innovation behavior, restaurant managers	integrating both quantitative and qualitative data
3	Ngo, Q. (2024)	The Impact of Green Market Orientation and Ambidextrous Green Innovation on Organizational Performance: Empirical Study on Small Restaurants in Vietnam	Green innovation, green market orientation, performance, restaurant	Quantitative method, online-survey
3	Montesdeoca-Calderón, M., Gil-Saura, I., Ruiz-Molina, M., & Martín-Ríos, C. (2024)	Does Employee Training in Sustainable Practices and Food Waste Influence a Restaurant's Level of Sustainability-Oriented Service Innovation (SOSI) and Brand Equity? Evidence-Based Research into the Ecuadorian Catering Industry	Segmentation, cluster analysis, discriminant analysis, sustainability	Quantitative method: surveys
3	Khan, S., Khan, S. U., & Mehmood, S. (2024)	Going green, going strong: maximising restaurant	Environmental strategy, food and services industry, Pakistan	Quantitative method: survey, 283 valid responses

		performance with sustainable practices		
3	Maia, B., Silva, S., Melo, A., Silva, G., Azevedo, D., Camões, H., & Melo, C. (2024)	Cooking Up a Sustainable Future: insights of Circular Economy in Restaurants	Circular economy, Sustainability, Restaurant Sector, Portugal	Qualitative method: semi-structured interviews
3	Weijers, R. J., Claessens, I. W. H., Gillebaart, M., & De Ridder, D. T. D. (2024)	Nudging towards sustainable dining: Exploring menu nudges to promote vegetarian meal choices in restaurants	Sustainable dining, taste perception, vegetarian	Quantitative method: online experiment

Appendix B. Data Requirement Table

Objective	Literature	Investigative Question	Variable(s) Required	Data Measured Details	Type of Question
All Objectives (Filtering Question)	N/A	Thinking about dining out, which statement best describes your experience with or interest in 'experiential' or 'multisensory' dining settings?	Level of prior interest or experience with multisensory dining	Single-choice response: (1) Frequently seek out, (2) Occasionally exposed, (3) Haven't tried but interested, (4) Only like traditional settings	Single choice (Screening)
Objective 1	Youssef & Spence (2023)	The visual presentation of dishes affected my perception of taste.	Perception of visual stimulation from food presentation	Level of agreement that visual presentation was stimulating	Likert Scale
Objective 1	Spence (2020)	The atmosphere of the restaurant (music, lighting, smells) enhanced my dining experience.	Perceived contribution of atmosphere	Level of agreement that atmosphere (lighting, music, scent) contributed	Likert Scale
Objective 1	Rottigni & Spence (2024)	The meal engaged (or would engage) multiple senses	Perception of unique multisensory engagement	Level of agreement on multisensory uniqueness	Likert Scale

		(sight, sound, smell, touch, taste) in a unique way.			
Objective 1	Yuan et al. (2022)	The physical textures of the space (e.g., furniture, tableware) influenced how I experienced the meal.	Perception of physical stimulation	Level of agreement on influence of space texture	Likert Scale
Objective 1	Spence (2020)	Aromas in the dining space shaped my appetite and emotional state, even before eating.	Perceived olfactory effects	Level of agreement on pre-meal olfactory effects	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Liu et al. (2023); Huang et al. (2023)	I would recommend this place for how it made me feel.	Perceived memorability	Level of agreement on emotional recommendation	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Tsaur & Lo (2020)	Considering the overall experience, it felt (or would feel) like good value for the money.	Value perception	Level of agreement on worthiness	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Velasco et al. (2024)	The dining experience created a	Perceived memorability	Level of agreement on memorability	Likert Scale

		memorable impression.			
Objective 2	Huang et al. (2023)	I would return even at a premium price point.	Willingness to return	Level of agreement on return willingness	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Jose et al. (2025)	Multisensory elements enhance value beyond fine dining.	Perception of added value	Level of agreement on enhancement beyond fine dining	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Malcman et al. (2024); Gao & Krashes (2024)	I consumed more than I needed due to the emotionally stimulating setting.	Behavioral response to environment	Level of agreement on overconsumption tendency	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Tahir et al. (2022); Mejia & Wilson (2024)	I rarely question sustainability claims (e.g., single-use decor, and imported ingredients) when I'm emotionally engaged by the experience	Consumer's priority: sensory vs. sustainability	Level of agreement on novelty > sustainability	Likert Scale
Objective 2	Tahir et al. (2022); Mejia & Wilson (2024)	I am less focused on mindful consumption (e.g., finishing everything,	Mindfulness in consumption	Level of agreement on reduced mindfulness	Likert Scale

		avoiding waste) when I'm highly engaged by a unique dining experience.			
Objective 3	Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu (2020); Liu et al. (2022)	I trust the aesthetic of high-end restaurants to imply responsible practices, even without proof.	Perception of ethical practice by aesthetics	Level of agreement on default ethical perception	Likert Scale
Objective 3	Ngo (2024); Khan et al. (2024)	Ethical transparency (e.g., showing food waste levels, local sourcing proof) would enhance rather than spoil my dining experience.	Effect of transparency	Level of agreement on enhanced enjoyment	Likert Scale
Objective 3	Yarış & Yazıcıoğlu (2020); Guachalla (2022)	I would be more impressed if a restaurant created a luxurious, emotional experience without harming the planet.	Impact of sustainable design	Level of agreement on impression by sustainability	Likert Scale

Appendix C. Full Survey Text

Exploring Multisensory Dining Experiences and Consumer Perceptions.

Introduction

Dear Participant,

You are invited to participate in a research study investigating how sensory factors in dining environments influence your perception, decision-making, and sustainability-related behaviours. The study aims to help develop dining concepts that are both engaging and environmentally responsible.

- The survey takes approximately **7–12 minutes** to complete.
- Your **participation is voluntary**, and you may withdraw at any time without giving a reason.
- Your responses are **anonymous and confidential**.
- No personal information will be collected (e.g., name or email).
- The data will be stored securely and used **only for academic research purposes** in partial fulfillment of a Bachelor's degree at GIHE.
- If you are a **student at Glion Institute of Higher Education**, kindly refrain from participating to maintain the study's integrity.

By proceeding, you acknowledge you have read this information and voluntarily consent to participate.

Section 1: Filtering Questions

FQ1. Thinking about dining out, which statement best describes your experience with or interest in 'experiential' or 'multisensory' dining settings (e.g., restaurants focusing heavily on unique atmosphere, themed concepts, creative presentation, sound, scent, etc.)?

- I frequently seek out and have experienced unique or 'experiential' dining settings.
- I have occasionally tried unique or 'experiential' dining settings.
- I haven't tried such settings yet, but I am interested in experiencing them.
- I generally prefer traditional dining settings and am not particularly interested in experiential ones.

Note: If you selected the last option, thank you for your interest. This survey focuses on individuals who have experienced or are interested in experiential dining. Your participation is not required further.

Section 2: Sensory Experience

Please think about a recent memorable 'experiential' or 'multisensory' dining experience you've had (or imagine one you would be interested in). Indicate your agreement with the following statements using the scale: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree.

SensoryExp_Item1. The visual presentation of dishes affected my perception of taste.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SensoryExp_Item2. The atmosphere of the restaurant (music, lighting, smells) enhanced my dining experience.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SensoryExp_Item3. The meal engaged (or would engage) multiple senses (sight, sound, smell, touch, taste) in a unique way.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SensoryExp_Item4. The physical textures of the space (e.g., furniture, tableware) influenced how I experienced the meal.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SensoryExp_Item5. Aromas in the dining space shaped my appetite and emotional state, even before eating.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Section 3: Perceived Value

Thinking about the same dining experience, please indicate your agreement with the following statements using the scale: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree.

PerceivedValue_Item1. I would recommend this place not for the food alone but for how it made me feel.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

PerceivedValue_Item2. Considering the overall experience, it felt (or would feel) like good value for the money.

- Strongly Disagree

- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

PerceivedValue_Item3. The dining experience created (or would create) a memorable impression.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

PerceivedValue_Item4. I would return to such an experience even at a premium price point.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

PerceivedValue_Item5. The multisensory elements made the experience feel worth more than a standard fine-dining meal.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Section 4: Sustainability Behaviour and Intentions

Thinking about your behavior and priorities in such unique/experiential dining settings, please indicate your agreement with the following statements using the

scale: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree.

SustainBehav_Item1. I consumed more than I needed due to the emotionally stimulating setting.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SustainBehav_Item2. I rarely question sustainability claims (e.g., single-use decor, and imported ingredients) when I'm emotionally engaged by the experience.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SustainBehav_Item3. I am less focused on mindful consumption (e.g., finishing everything, avoiding waste) when I'm highly engaged by a unique dining experience.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SustainBehav_Item4. I trust the aesthetic of high-end restaurants to imply responsible practices, even without proof.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SustainBehav_Item5. Ethical transparency (e.g., showing food waste levels, local sourcing proof) would enhance rather than spoil my dining experience.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

SustainBehav_Item6. I would be more impressed if a restaurant created a luxurious, emotional experience without harming the planet.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Conclusion

Thank you for completing this survey. Your insights are valuable for understanding the complexities of modern dining experiences and exploring ways to balance creativity with responsibility in the hospitality industry.